

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF HEALTHY THINKING IN STUDENTS

Odiljonova Kholbuvi

Trainee teacher of the Department of General psychology, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

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Abstract. *This article studies the problems of harmonious formation of students' independent and healthy thinking, healthy thinking, independence in decision-making, responsibility, the formation of their own ideas and thoughts. The psychological features of the formation of healthy thinking among students are highlighted.*

Keywords: *thinking, healthy thinking, idea and thought, economic and intellectual potential, development of science and culture, perception, perception, imagination.*

The role of our country in the world economy, its economic and intellectual potential, its contribution to the development of Science and culture are determined by the standard of living of our people. The Uzbek people have long been distinguished by their childhood, familiarity. Loving the child, making their belly full and their top idol in their own way, but raising our children on the basis of national upbringing morality, high spirituality and healthy thinking from the very beginning of youth has always been of urgent importance.

The analysis of studies, scientific treatises and articles related to the problems of the formation and development of human thinking has shown that the problem of thinking, healthy thinking and the appearance of human thinking as an object of discussion, scientists are in close attention. M.G.Davletshin, E.G'.Goziev, V.M.Karimova, Z.T.Nishanova, Sh.Shodmonova, J.Musaev, S.The atakhanovas covered the problem we raised, namely, in their research, harmonizing the problems of thought education, logic, creative, critical and independent thought expression, the formation of independent and healthy thinking. M.G.Davletshin pays great attention to the development of independent thinking in students. The scientist noted that " the main task of current schools is to improve educational methods. When it comes to the tasks of the school one can dwell on the level of thinking that is much more suitable for understanding the science that is now being taught, the current socio – political relationship. These requirements are met by the scientific-theoretical (dialectical) level of thinking" .

Several studies have been carried out by scientists of our country on thinking and its manifestations (creative, logical, artistic-aesthetic, moral, environmental, independence, historical). Perhaps this situation is due to the point of view theory that common sense applies to all forms of thinking. As you know, the effectiveness of the reforms carried out in all spheres of our society is inextricably linked, first of all, with the restoration of folk spirituality, a deep study of our rich historical heritage, the preservation of our traditions, the development of Culture, Art, Science and education, the training of qualified specialist personnel armed with technical achievements of modern science.

So we are not mistaken to say that with the rise of a person's spirituality, his thinking and thinking also develop. After all, thinking is a high form of human mental activity, the most important connections and relationships between things and phenomena are reflected in our minds. Through contemplation, we have the opportunity to know the essence of things and phenomena in the material world, and therefore direct perception, perception, imagination and thinking play an

important role in knowing the world. Thinking is a high form of human mental activity. Thinking is a weapon of knowledge of the surrounding world and is a prerequisite for the emergence of rational practical activity of a person.

Reality is reflected in thinking more directly and fully than in perception and imagination.

Contemplation is a generalizing reflection of reality. The most important connections and relationships between things or phenomena are opened with the help of contemplation.

Consequently, thinking is such a mental activity of a person that this activity allows you to reflect (know) reality most clearly (correctly), fully, deeply and generalizing, allowing a person to engage in a more rational practical activity.

As schoolchildren begin to acquire knowledge, they also learn to justify, prove, reject, verify various rules. In particular, they learn to use examples, facts, general rules, and axioms as arguments. High school students, especially students of the upper classes, are able to reveal contradictions, irrationality, unsubstantiated aspects in complex discussions of others, as well as their own. Native language, arithmetic training, is especially of great importance for the growth of critical, proven thinking. Schoolchildren always use arguments that prove and refute in training on the basics of socio-historical science and Darwinism. The participation of schoolchildren in amateur circles, active participation in the discussion of the issues seen, plays a big role in the growth and development of critical, proven and independent thinking. During the period of teaching children, in combination with theoretical thinking, practical thinking is also developed in them. First of all, this is achieved in such a way that the teaching of most subjects in the school (for example, Physics, Chemistry, Botany, Zoology) is carried out in connection with the application of the knowledge received by students in industry, agriculture. Schoolchildren believe that the growth and development of thinking will not be even and the same. The individual characteristics of students are determined to a large extent by the growth of other psychic processes - memory, imagination, speech, attention, will; these individual characteristics are in many ways related to the interests of students, their activity in educational and practical work, as well as the self-education of students will depend. Educational work in secondary schools is carried out with the active, conscious participation of students. Therefore, our school helps to a large extent the growth of a wide range of meaningful, exceptional and logically correct thinking in children. K.P. Megrelidze argues that any mental phenomenon in a person cannot be properly explained without taking into account the social factor. This thing depends primarily on human thinking. Thinking cannot be studied without other manifestations of social life. The methods of human thinking are not in the nervous system, nor in the brain, but in the social conditions that in one period give way to such perception, thinking, working, and in another period to work nerve activity differently.

Human thoughts and views are caused not by individual order, but by social relations, about which Megrelidze writes: "human thought moves not according to natural and biological laws, but on the path of socio-historical laws. The way a person thinks is primarily a social phenomenon. The opinion of a separate individual is a private manifestation of socially expressed thoughts. Each individual person thinks with the help of social concepts and visions.

Thoughts and ideas are not the product of free individual creativity, but the product of society and social monasteries, such as the individual himself. Therefore, the solution to the puzzle about human thinking, stages of thinking, forms and methods of human thinking should be sought not from logical research, not from traditional psychology, but first of all from the social origin of

these ideas. One way or another, individ remains a "random" expressiveness of social ideas set forth in society".

A special place in Uzbek families is occupied by spiritual heritage created by ancestral thought and intelligence. Material and spiritual monuments created by the thought and genius of our ancestors, from samples of folk oral creativity, thousands of manuscripts preserved in the treasures of our libraries today, valuable works on history, literature, art, politics, ethics, philosophy, medicine, mathematics, astronomy, architecture, agriculture and other fields embodied in them are our great spiritual wealth. It is on the basis of these that it is important to educate the younger generation. In this case, special attention should be paid to further improving the activities of cooperation between the family and the educational institution. After all, spiritual culture in the family is also associated with the actions of family members, the potential to assess reality, moral knowledge and experiences, the ability to use them, the differentiation of good-bad, positive-negative situations and hakoza factors.

But happiness is not determined only by wealth, property. A decent, knowledgeable and intelligent, hardworking child is the greatest asset not only of the parents, but of the whole society. Therefore, to educate our youth a harmonious generation with a physically healthy, spiritually mature and independent mind, to strengthen the family, which is a stronghold of spirituality, where the eternity of life ensures the continuity of generations today. The only idea that, regardless of the hurficrism that exists in our society today, jeeps young people, protects the inviolability of our people and our state, encourages el-Yut to higher goals – to educate in the spirit of loyalty to the national ideology-constitutes the essence of today. S.Atakhanova touched on the issue of the formation of Healthy Thinking in student-youth and came to the following conclusion: --first, to educate them spiritually-aesthetically,

- secondly, to form their active point of view on problems in the life of society,

- thirdly, it becomes the basis for their interpretation in the perspective as a social group that protects the health of the whole society. Therefore, healthy thinking is desirable if it is considered as a means of ensuring the personal perfection of students and young people.

When it comes to the set of pedagogical-psychological measures and processes in the development of Healthy Thinking in students, it is necessary to first assume that healthy thinking is both a psychological, philosophical and pedagogical category. Because, healthy thinking embodies them all in its meaning. If we focus only on the pedagogical-psychological aspects of healthy thinking, it becomes clear that several specific stages and processes take place in the formation of healthy thinking. They are:

a) the process of analyzing previous knowledge and skills, social status and experiences in itself. The main feature of this process is that the essence of the existing concept is divided into certain units that make it up, that is, the components of the concept are separated. At the same time, the set of competencies of this concept, firstly, a set of knowledge, and secondly, separately, is sorted and determined;

b) the process of synthesizing existing knowledge and skills. In the previous process, it is clarified the nature of the generalization of the concept, which is specially divided into units, arising from today's demand;

D) the process of comparative comparison, on the basis of a comparative study of all available knowledge and skills, the specific aspects in them that are similar and different are

understood and accepted. This process contributes to a clearer understanding of the relevance within the constituent parts of the concept, the content of mutually complementary factors;

e) the process of classification, all knowledge and skills related to healthy thinking, its components and content are grouped by combining existing characteristics. Grouping creates the possibility of a holistic picture of the essence of the concept in general. Grouping helps to understand the logic within the content of the concept. In classification, grouping is carried out on the basis of the characteristics of the components.

f) in the process of generalization, knowledge and skills related to healthy thinking are grouped on the basis of the most common parties and characteristics present in them;

j) in the process of clarification, the private aspects of the concept of healthy thinking are distinguished from its common aspects. That is, clarity is introduced into the internal private aspects of each concept within healthy thinking, which is then summarized;

h) the process of abstraction directs one aspect of healthy thinking to intensify and exaggerate awareness without taking into account others. That is, healthy thinking actually acquires modernity with several dozen different facets of itself. It is in this process that one aspect of healthy thinking can be more relevant today than the other aspects. But later, after positive changes in social reality, this relevance can free up its place for other problems. For example, from the problems that are most important in the system of knowledge and skills in the framework of healthy thinking today, issues such as AIDS, norcamania among young people, Toxicamania, human trafficking require a special emphasis on these very edges in recent decades.

The researcher noted that in order for these stages to form a healthy thinking, each person, to one degree or another, must consciously go through all pedagogical-psychological stages. Only when a person goes through these stages can knowledge and skills be formed in his thinking in the framework of all the required Healthy Thinking, completely and perfectly.

To form a healthy mindset, the teacher in the educational process determines the general and individual characteristics of students, the possibilities of mental abilities, the indicator of mental growth, content, the depth and depth of Thought, initiative and productivity, the student's interest in educational subjects, speech culture and vocabulary, personal positivity and point of view, beliefs and worldview, the degree of – particular attention to self-capture, concern for health, the level of the knowledge system, learning skills and qualifications, the form of reasoning (judgment, inference, the possibility of using concepts, terms), logic opera (justification, proof, argument, research, confidence) is a guarantee of improving the effectiveness of training.

Practical experience is currently putting the following urgent problems on the agenda, which should be solved in cooperation with the family, neighborhood and educational institution of the development of Healthy Thinking in students, according to which;

- 1) development of Healthy Thinking in students;
- 2) formation and development of spiritual and moral qualities in students;
- 3) to further enrich students' knowledge of such concepts as family, neighborhood, acquisition of knowledge, love for the motherland, peace of the land, which are part of the universal value system;
- 4) content the "culture of information" through the development of critical thinking in students;

5) formation of healthy thinking through enrichment of pedagogical and psychological knowledge of students, effective organization of healthy lifestyle and forms of cooperation of family and educational institution;

6) to protect students from tobelik to Internet and computer games, etc.

It is from early adolescence that the development of Healthy Thinking in students is one of the pressing problems of pedagogy-psychology. Because, healthy thinking allows a person to analyze, synthesize the knowledge he is learning. On the basis of the accumulated knowledge, however, observation helps to find the most correct, concise and effective way to understand News, ideas, new knowledge and solve problems. Healthy Thinking is important in the reader-youth in decision-making, independence, responsibility, in the formation of his own ideas and thoughts, in the reaction to what is happening in social life. Healthy Thinking is important for the reader – youth in decision-making independence, responsibility, in the formation of his own ideas and thoughts, in the reaction to what is happening in social life. Attention was paid to studying the concept of healthy thinking, the pedagogical problem, the essence of its current state of development of Healthy Thinking in students

American educator-psychologist Dj.Dewey is one of the scientists who studied the Social Psychological essence of thinking in connection with the problem of thought education. In his view: "experience and knowledge are the source of thought. If the person is partially familiar with the problem, they may think to solve the problem. The individual does not think if there is a problem in front of the individual without experience involving such conditions" .

According to scientists, admiration is the mother of any science. Therefore, the teacher's task is not to quench the spark of surprise in the student, to set fire to the flame of curiosity, and to educate the approach to what is happening around and events through Musha.

John Dewey attributed the development of thinking to the genesis of human development, believing that among all its factors, the child's habit of striving for an external social environment is important. The child initially acquires vital and social knowledge in the family. So, based on the above information, we can interpret the content of the concept of "healthy thinking" as follows: and on the basis of the accumulated knowledge, it helps to find the most correct, concise and effective way to observe, understand News, ideas, new knowledge and solve problems. As such, reforms in the field of Education:

- to positively influence the socio-political climate, to completely change the existing environment in the country as a whole;

- to the formation of an independent thinking free personality in society;

- aimed at educating perfect people with general and special knowledge, conscious, free of thought, a modern and broad worldview, successor to national and universal values, building a strong civil society. In the process of cooperation of the family, neighborhood, educational institution in the formation of Healthy Thinking in the student-youth, the vaifas of the neighborhood are:

- the activity of neighborhood activists, together with educational institutions, in discussing issues that should be carried out in the educational process and finding rational solutions;

- to discuss spiritually unhealthy families at neighborhood gatherings, to take public measures towards them;

- support the provision of economic and social assistance to educational institutions in the neighborhood area;

Through the direction of National Education, the qualities of self-awareness, patriotism, national pride, culture of interethnic communication, national ideological awareness, national decency, dedication are formed in young people. In the educational process, it is important to treat the student as the main subject, take into account the individual and psychological characteristics of the child in the teaching process, effectively use methods of communicative influence in the development of knowledge, thinking of students in increasing the effectiveness of teaching, study of the development of Healthy Thinking in students as a pedagogical problem, as well

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